

Review Article

Faculties' Professional Development in Higher Education of Nepal: Exploring Practice Challenges and Prospects

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Abstract

The University Grants Commission has provisioned to make policies and programs for faculties' professional development and universities are enacting professional enrichment program in higher education in Nepal. The faculties are seeking higher attention in pedagogical advancement and technology driven instructional strategies. The professional tenure lacks in accelerating with great momentum despite the higher education policy and provision in Nepal. The insight and prospects from the university faculties can promote structural reframing of professional developmental opportunities to combat global challenges in education promoting quality education. This study intends to explore the experience of faculties in the constituent campus of Tribhuvan University concerning professional development policy and practice Employing the qualitative case study (Yazan, 2015) constituent colleges of Tribhuvan University were taken purposively as research sites. Four faculties from each college were selected voluntarily. Semi-structured interviews were taken with faculties who have more than ten years of experience and responses were transcribed as verbatim. The data were thematically analyzed by generating code through in-depth immersion in the information. The study examined the challenges such as pedagogical innovation being pressurized by societal engagement, lack of technology integration with administrative hurdles, limited training and seminar attendance opportunities, unable to balance teaching research and academic tasks, and lack of Interdisciplinary collaboration. Based upon the above findings the university can design effective strategies and support systems for empowering teachers in their professional careers.

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1. Introduction

Two types of universities are in existence to deliver higher education in Nepal. One of them is completely funded by the government through the University Grants Commission and others are privately run in their entire management. In these all

types of universities, the higher education systems intersect and coincide with the service delivery model (Fenyöet al., 2017)^[5]. The newly germinated universities are delivering education similar to the program of the old university. The overall management and education delivery systems are the same and

the identity is different (Baral, 2016)^[3]. The mechanism for the human resource system is slightly different but there is a clear systematic mechanism for professional development of university teachers. In the government-funded university, constituent and affiliated campuses are large in numbers and the teachers are politically fragmented with their separate associations. Generally, the teacher's associations are falling behind in the aspect of developing professional development parameters but instead raise the issue of promotion directly at a certain period (Panthee *et al.*, 2023)^[9]. Most of the teachers are free from teaching and learning and want recommended official posts by nearing to the political leaders. Such types of teachers are reluctant about research, innovation and updated knowledge. In every government change they get the opportunity from the affiliated organization (Baral *et al.*, 2016)^[3]. In the dynamic landscape of higher education, university faculties play a pivotal role in shaping the academic and personal growth of students (Tantawy *et al.*, 2020)^[15]. This role shares varied nature of challenges, which requires continuous professional development activities to navigate themselves. The evolving educational paradigm, technological advancement and diverse student expectations exhibit a set of complexities that need educators to adapt and enhance their skills (MacPhail *et al.*, 2019)^[8]. Due to the increasing trend in college and university, either in physical or virtual mode competition has been tremendously increased. The faculty's member needs to be equipped with quality education product to prevent the brain drain problem of the nation.

In the context of Nepal, higher education is increasing rapidly with great ambition. The practice and mission are roaming in the same nature even though the consensus is different. In higher education in Nepal, the role of the teacher is expected to be great and supportive of leading the society. The momentum of knowledge is frequently speeded to the updated local and global issues (Bajracharya *et al.*, 2020). The pre-service courses are outdated day by day with the emergence of complications in society. The nation requires an internal rate of return from education with a result basis (Baral *et al.*, 2016)^[3]. In this context, the higher education teacher needs to extend his horizon as a researcher, curriculum developer, leader, policy maker and counselor in an extended program (Nepali & Baralet *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, the teachers in higher education need to be groomed with extremely professional skills for leading effective teaching.

In the above landscape, this study intends to explore the key professional development challenges and coping strategies to mitigate or overcome these challenges as experienced by university teachers to ensure a vibrant and effective learning environment.

2. Statement of the Problem

The professional development of university teachers in the modern landscape of higher education is influenced by the rapid and evolving dynamics of significant challenges encompassing the range of factors that impact the effectiveness of teaching and the overall learning experience of students

(Parvin *et al.*, 2018)^[11]. As university intends to prepare higher-skilled manpower that can contribute to the development of nation for inclusive growth with micro and macroeconomic dimensions (Ali *et al.*, 2021). The university makes every effort to meet the demands of an increasingly diverse and technology-driven educational environment. The teacher are unable to find coping strategy for the issues related to pedagogical approaches, technological integration, student engagement and the need to foster inclusivity (Parvinet *et al.*, 2018)^[11].

The lapses embedded in traditional teaching methods in addressing the challenges evolved to emphasize the urgency for university teaching to embark on a journey of continuous professional development (Singh *et al.*, 2008)^[14]. It sheds light on their implication and the potential pathways for educators to enhance their skills and adapt to the evolving demands of higher education effectively (MacPhail *et al.*, 2019)^[8]. About higher education institutes in Nepal, the trend is accelerated with the traditional mode of teaching with unproductive strategies still failing to crosscut the societal and global challenges. Tribhuvan University has endorsed a semester system with the intent of profound use of faculty's cognitive knowledge and skills for student development. However, the university could not cultivate a faculty development mechanism along the lines of societal dynamics (Thapa *et al.*, 2019)^[16]. However, the teaching strategies and accomplishments have remained in the same position. The faculties in the colleges are behind in the professional development goal due to the excessive work load and varied individual pressure (Khanal *et al.*, 2020).^[7] The teachers themselves are unwilling to empower with professional efficacy due to the imbalanced provision offered in university. The motivations of faculties in professional development realm are deviated from the matter of interest (Regmiet *et al.*, 2021)^[13]. In this context, study is intended to highlight experience on professional development practice provisioned in higher education of Nepal and its impact on higher education landscape.

3. Objectives

1. To determine the status of professional development opportunities available to constituent campus faculties.
2. To identify the challenges of teaching and accessing coping strategies for upgrading higher education.
3. To study the dimension of professional development and its key relation with the development of higher education.

Research question

1. How do faculties of constituent campuses perceive professional development opportunities in higher education for professional efficacy?
2. What challenges do the teachers face in line with professional development in their teaching career?
3. What strategies can institutions use to design professional development opportunities that increase their engagement in teaching and learning for professionals?

4. Literature Review

Historical Landscape in Higher Education in Nepal

The educational history of Nepal formally started with the establishment of Durbar School in 1910 BS during the Rana regime. That was confined to the Rana family only not provisioned for the public. The public people had to access education only after the restoration of democracy in 2007 BS. After this period, schools were mushroomed everywhere in different parts of the country. Concerning higher education, it had been started from Trichandra Campus in Kathmandu with the affiliation of Patna University India in 1918 AD. The postgraduate courses in humanities and social science were offered but the exam was conducted by Patna University until 1962. Later on, National College at present Shankar Dev Campus was established in 1951AD. Likewise, Thakur Ram Multiple Campus, Birgunj was established in 1952 AD. During this period, National Education Commission was formed and recommended establishing a new university. Therefore, the government of Nepal established Tribhuvan University with TU Charter. The government of Nepal formed the University Grants Commission in 1956 AD to provide grants and allocate financial resources for higher education. Later on, Mahendra Sanskrit University was established in 1986, Kathmandu University in 1991, Purbaanchal University in 1993, and Pokhara University in 1997. At present altogether 11 including TU, PU, PoU, LBU, MWU, FWU, NOU, RJU, and GU are providing higher education. 1436 higher education institutions affiliated with different universities are serving students with higher education. 183 higher education institutions affiliated with foreign Universities are offering A-level courses in Nepal. Six health sciences academics BPKHS, NAMS, Patan Academy of Health Science, Karnali Academy of Health Science, Pokhara Academy of Health Science, and Rapti Academy of Health Science are providing technical education as university standard. The universities are offering higher education in various disciplines in different degrees. The enrollment ratio of higher education is 15% (National Education Policy, 2016) which is half of the global context and 12% less than the Asia Pacific countries like India and Vietnam (Joshiet *et al.*, 2018)^[6].

Professional Development status in higher education in Nepal

Teacher education embraces procedures that are designed to prepare competent teachers with knowledge and skills. In the great potential teacher can perform their responsibility by efficiently and enthusiastically in the classroom. With professional development activities, the teacher can become an expert in fulfilling needs and coping with professional challenges (Ali *et al.*, 2021)^[1]. The formal and non-formal activity that assists a person in developing innate power bears any responsibility of the education domain (MacPhail *et al.*, 2019)^[8]. The University Grants Commission approved by parliament in 1993 disperses financial support for higher education to universities allocated by the government through the Ministry of Education (UGC, 2014 p.29). UGC makes plans,

policies and programs to promote the quality of education. It is also responsible for making necessary arrangements for the exchange of facilities and fellowship to the faculties and students of universities in various extremes (UGC, 2010). Concerning the professional development of teachers in higher education, the Nepal National Education Planning Commission (NNEPC) 2011 recommended establishing teacher education college and the college of education was established in 1956 with the financial and technical support of US. This was owned by TU after its establishment in 1959 and renamed as Institute of Education in 1971 and later on Faculty of Education at present. The major purpose of teacher education is to develop trained teachers for primary and secondary level, education planners, trainers and policymakers. Half of the total 11 universities established in Nepal have teacher education programs. The professional development activities are governed by UGC under the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology.

Professional development opportunity is essential for keeping a balance between teaching accountability and research activities in higher education in Nepal. Minimum time allotment for teaching and innovative works is strictly followed. The faculties are encouraged to participate in research and academic development by providing incentives and study leave with pay and limited funding support for higher study (Bista *et al.*, 2019)^[4]. The provision for professional development activities including seminar participation, writing indexed journal articles and books seemed to be small, not enough to cover the actual costs involved. The faculties need MPhil and PhD degrees for promotion but it is not considered a quality of faculty (Thapa *et al.*, 2019)^[16]. Pre-service training and experience are not required for an initial appointment in this job.

The faculty lacks academic productivity regarding research; publication and participation in academic workshops, seminars and conferences however, these activities help add merit points to faculty requirements and promotion. The faculty member keeps stereotypical thoughts in pursuing higher degrees such as MPhil or PhD due to the ill practice of political party. By dirty political practice, the faculty without academic Excellency can grave the opportunity under the security of the ruling political party. The UGC Nepal is providing scholarship and research grants to academics on a competitive basis for quality enhancement and developing a national system for evaluating faculty in higher education. The system is not functioning well and requires more harnesses. It requires an authentic program for pedagogical and instructional training for university faculty in terms of pre-service and in-service refreshers. There should also be resource centers that could provide technical and professional support services to university faculty, and help them keep abreast of Instructional methods and resources, including the uses of information and Communication Technology (ICT). In addition, most importantly, there is a need to support and motivate faculty to continuously engage in research and professional development.

Teacher's perception towards professional development in higher education

Professional development is a capability that capacitates to encourage students with improved learning outcomes (Kanpp *et al.*, 2003). The teacher can maintain a consistent practice in the classroom with the help of their experience, knowledge and expertise. The teacher's professional development is accompanied by formal and structural settings like seminars, workshops and long-term training programs. Sometimes it is obtained through university graduate courses after certain duration (Wilson & Berne *et al.*, 1999). Some teacher can achieve professionalism through self-effort such as research and innovation with their career skill.

Researchers (Shah *et al.*, 2022) looked at teacher's perceptions of harmful practices and professional growth in Pakistani higher education institutions. The purpose of this study was to investigate how teachers view professional development and harmful practices related to it. For this study, a phenomenological research design was chosen. Interviews were conducted with 30 teachers using a convenient sample and semi-structured interview protocols. It is crucial to report on teacher professional development. Ineffective and conventional teaching methods, impolite and abrupt classroom conduct, and invalid and void practices are examples of eccentric classroom instruction. The outcomes have an impact on organizational restrictions on professional development in higher education and insufficient training.

In the study (Alruqi *et al.*, 2022)^[2], the author intended to explore the relationship between school environment and teacher readiness for professional development and insight into the impact on professional quality, and career progression. The semi-structured interview was taken with three English teachers. The result showed that there is a positive influence of professional development on their performance personal qualities, student outcomes, career progression and commitment to the profession.

In the above study, the teacher needs professional development opportunities to enhance their horizon in the profession. Conventional teaching strategies can demolish the progressive path of teaching careers in higher education. The continuous approach towards professional development makes an individual more ethical and efficient.

5. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative interpretive case study design (Yin *et al.*, 2009) focusing on constituent campuses as the case for exploring experience in professional development situations. An instrumental case is designed to explore the specific issue, problem or concern with the case or cases (Cresswell *et al.*, 2013). A particular case study intends to explore the emerging phenomena in their real context with the question of how and why (Yin *et al.*, 2009). This design is appropriate for exploring challenges that university teachers face in their professional development in teaching careers. One constituent campus and one public campus located in Kathmandu Valley are purposively selected with four teachers

teaching Nepali and English as per campus. Altogether six participants containing three from each participant college were selected. The findings reported in this paper are extracted from two cases: constituent campus teacher and public campus teacher. These campuses were selected because of among other factors their age and that they were typical cases. Terms of ages the constituent campus teachers were older than public campus teachers, so they could be informative cases. In-depth interviews were taken from selected participant via semi-structured interview guidelines focusing on challenges and factors to mitigate these challenges from their inner expertise.

6. Result and Discussion

The University teachers experience many professional development challenges that seeks to innovative teaching and smooth professional career (Raj Kumar Baral *et al.*)^[3]. The prospect and insight of faculties differ in regard to professional trajectory depending on the institution, field of study, and personal circumstances (Pesce *et al.*, 2015). The experience and insight of university teacher in professional tenure are thematically discussed and challenges and coping strategies are delved with the essence of literature support.

Opportunity of Training

Training refers to the knowledge construction process based on need and interest offered for a short time to energize their efficiency. Attending training, seminars and workshops capacitates into workforce to obtain better results than expected. It also updates the existing knowledge into innovative new knowledge for their career development.

Participant PT1 said,

I have been teaching for more than fifteen years at the bachelor's well as master's levels. I have been teaching the same content as I studied at the same level. The paradigm has shifted in pedagogy in the world but our teaching method remains unchanged have not heard of the opportunity that the university and campus offered seminar and workshop training for university teachers concerning pedagogy.

In the above concern, the teachers are beyond the training opportunity in their career period. Today, knowledge has exploded within a second. With the rapid advancement of knowledge, the teaching contents, and pedagogy have been innovated accordingly. The teacher needs to disseminate new knowledge and skills for students to tackle societal challenges. Only the teacher can guide the student with new knowledge and skills. In this context, the teacher needs to be empowered with advanced technology and skills. The universities need to organize refreshment training and initiate workshops and seminars to strengthen the capacity of faculties.

Another participant PT2 said,

I have the responsibility of teaching economics at the master's level. At the time of my study, we should not have studied the mathematical portion of economics. Now the course has been changed and mathematical content is integrated but I am

unable to teach. It is better to train old economist teachers to teach qualitative analysis at this level. Otherwise, we could not deliver effective instruction for master-level students.

Concerning the above narratives, the teachers having old courses are unable to teach the new content with their old knowledge. The teacher himself is not ignorant of old knowledge because the knowledge that the teacher has is new and innovative in that context but now it is outdated with the changed societal context. Anyway, the teachers need to be fostered with updated skills and knowledge with new content. In this context, the university needs to organize a subject and content-specific workshop with a subject expert in every course amendment and initiate training with advanced technology. Workshop for making modules also needs to be organized for pre-service and in-service teachers with essential facilities. Another participant PT3 said,

I have been teaching in higher education since 2003 with the traditional teaching method. The formal education system has been changed into a semester system with the aim of quality education. The aim of introducing a semester system is to produce qualitative work force for the development of the nation but the education system remains the same as the annual system. The semester brought system modification but not effective systemic change. In the name of the semester, only the teacher got the benefit and students became free of hard work. The semester courses have been made by splitting the annual course not based upon the market demand.

In the above concern, the paradigm has been changed into an education system to impart quality education through a constructivist approach but the teachers are practicing the same conventional pedagogy. The content preparation for teachers in new content is becoming challenging with the existing references. The training for module construction is frequently flourished to prepare for effective instruction. Technology-based instruction is highly encouraged with the dissemination of advanced technical skills.

Workshop and seminar attendant

The active involvement of teacher for bolstering of their capacity with the relevant knowledge and skill embarks with professional development. The mutual sharing of ideas in the focused area can sharpen their professional strength. In this context Participant PT4 said,

I have been teaching at the university level for the last 15 years. Regarding experience, I think of myself as an old teacher but the subject committee has not informed me about any academic activity performed in the aspect of professional development. The hidden potentiality is not exposed due to the mal political practice. The teachers are not provided an opportunity to develop their inner powers. It is not thought that developing expertise is an asset of a university.

In the above concern, some of the teacher has not grabbed the opportunity to faculty development. Due to the malpractice of various factors, he is marginalized in professional development. The university and campuses should offer the opportunity to participate in all the faculties from whatever the background. The faculty needs to be equipped with advanced knowledge and skills from the right-based approach. The faculties need to be provided sufficient funds to attend conferences, workshops, and other events related to their field. This helps them stay updated with the latest developments and connect with peers in their discipline.

Balancing Teaching, Research and Service

University teachers are typically expected to excel in three main areas: teaching, research, and service. Balancing these demands can be challenging, especially for early-career academics who are trying to establish themselves in their field. In this context participant PT1 said,

Since I began my teaching career I have not had the opportunity to carry out the research. When I submit the research proposal for a specific issue to the research division in the university, I will be disqualified because I cannot access that office with a recommendation. The announced research projects are limited and selected based on affiliation rather than quality. The proposal selection mechanism is not fair and issue-based.

In the above context, the teacher himself has no access to the research division and is far from the research opportunity. All the faculties need to have equal responsibility and accountability for upgrading the university. The faculties who are interested in carrying out the research in his area must have an equal chance of being selected based on the issue raised. No subject needs to be preferable with recommendation. All subjects should have equal value and importance. The universities need to allocate resources and time for faculty members to engage in research activities. This includes funding for research projects, access to research facilities, and support for publishing. Another participant PT2 said,

With the existing facilities offered by the university, I cannot accomplish any research project and it is not validated. Doing research should be validated by an authentic organization. Most of the teachers are falling behind from the research opportunity and their service is inclined to be traditional. Without research delivering high-quality education, engaging lectures, and managing diverse students' needs are impossible.

In the above concern, the faculty seems reluctant to carry out the research project due to various reasons like funds, time and many more. If he with his effort carries out research, he may not be validated by authentic organization. In the absence of research-based knowledge, the instruction delivery model falls into the traditional approach and students become weak with their intellectual development. Another participant PT2 said,

In higher education the course contents need to be continuously updated to match the evolving needs of society. The higher level manpower should address the emerging demand of people by their education. Only innovative teaching with pedagogical advancement can feed essential knowledge to cope with the constant challenges.

Concerning to above context, higher education curriculum has been frequently amended to address the needs of society. Higher education should produce higher-level work force to contribute to the transformation of society. Advanced pedagogy with updated knowledge can contribute to the nation's development. The prospective campus needs to create teaching and learning centers on campus that offer resources, training, and support for faculty members to enhance their teaching skills and explore innovative pedagogical approaches.

Research productivity

It refers to the innovative activity that enhances the capabilities of teachers to be confident. With the accomplishment of research work, the teacher can apply novel ideas and competency for teaching. This propels teachers to generate new ideas and pedagogical refinement to the instructional delivery. In this context, a participant PT2 said,

Conducting impactful research and publishing in reputable journals is essential for academic advancement. However due to the financial pressure that has been created to accomplish such research that contributes to the field. We the faculties ourselves suffered from financial limitations as well as family hurdles.

Concerning the above, carrying out impactful research is unaffordable for university teachers. Likewise publishing an article in a reputable journal is also costly and far from his financial horizon. In other words, the faculties are facing family pressure instead of attending to research activity freely. Therefore, university needs to provide funding for faculty development works such as doing research, and publishing articles in impact journals. By using human capital theory, investment in education needs to increase for the betterment of a professional career. Similarly, the faculties are provided financial facilities to attend conferences, workshops, and other events related to their field. This helps them stay updated with the latest developments and connect with peers in their discipline. In this context participant PT3said,

Securing research funding through grant application is a critical aspect of academic research. The eligible criteria for submitting the proposal do not support our existing level. Writing a successful grant proposal requires more time, effort specific skills and finance but we are lacking in this matter.

In the above context, the teacher's present level is not illegible for eminent academic research. The time and resources are inadequate for conducting valuable research. The teachers are themselves limited by financial condition. To overcome this situation the university needs to provide many opportunities to

participate in previously mentioned activity. So the university need to provide flexible work arrangement when possible allowing faculty to balance their teaching, research and personal commitments effectively. Participant PT4 said,

In writing a successful proposal, the advanced research methodology is an essential factor. Information and communication technology skill is equally needed to succeed in the proposal. It lacks research method logy training from the research division of the relevant organization. Sometimes the research management cell submits the proposal to UGC for research support and organizes short-term research methodology training if support is approved, otherwise not.

In the above context, accomplishing research is a more complicated job and it is costly and time-consuming. It needs to be supported by any organization. However, the research project under the funding support is not free of biases and is autonomous. The research findings should be in the interest of donor agencies. Such type of research cannot be valuable and socially contributed. For the sake of research productivity, the campuses need to manage funds every year by pointing out the issue. The announcement of the research proposal from the university is very limited concerning the realm of subject coverage. The horizon of research needs to be extended to address and explore local issues intersecting with a global context.

Personal Development

Personal development for a university teacher is a continuous process that involves enhancing teaching skills, expanding knowledge, and fostering professional growth. University teachers need to invest in their personal development to enhance their teaching and research skills. This might involve attending workshops, conferences, and training sessions.

In this context, a participant PT1 said,

I need to spend more time in preparation for course content with the knowledge I have. In addition to campus time, I need to engage in family work because full-time cannot be allotted for teaching. The facility provided by the university is insufficient for faculties and need to extend our knowledge into other occupations. Sometimes I need to accomplish social responsibility given by society.

Concerning to above, the individual teacher is consuming more time for content preparation for effective teaching. The teacher has studied the old course and now the context is new course should be taught. In some subjects, the content materials are not easily accessible to teachers. Library access is impossible for teachers and cannot afford to purchase that book. The teacher faces challenges in abstracting advanced knowledge with the previous references. In such a context teacher feels threatened to secure a job in the present context. So campuses need to organize course dissemination workshops to enhance the content capacity of teachers. Another participant PT2 said,

"Personal development is very much essential to effective instruction. Frequent attending in workshops, conferences and training cultivates the inner strength of faculties. The refreshment training support to faculties for gearing up their strength".

In this concern, the personal development of a teacher keeps the teacher updated with the latest advancements and research in the relevant field. Frequent attendance in conferences, workshops, seminars and continuous reading of academic journal supports to keep up to date with recent trends and developments. Likewise, achieving a higher degree or certificate related to own subject area enhances expertise and gives access to a wider network of professionals. The teaching techniques and methods are improved with continuous participation in pedagogy workshops, online courses and training sessions on effective teaching practice. With the development of personality, teachers need to innovate strategies to engage and motivate students. To make the learning experience more interactive and meaningful, active learning methods, group discussion and experiential learning need to be implemented. The university needs to offer varieties of professional development programs such as workshops, seminars and courses on teaching methods, research techniques, technology integration and leadership skills that are tailored to the needs of faculty members.

Peer observation and mentorship

The observation of class by one another for the expectation of constructive feedback and facilitating the exchange of effective teaching practice refers to peer observation. A mentorship program is an interactive program in which experienced faculty members guide and advise newer colleagues. This supports the transfer of valuable institutional knowledge and provides a supportive environment for career growth. In this context participant PT2 said,

The teachers are appointed from diverse backgrounds. They embark on different references across the learning condition in their time. Some of the teachers might have a smooth situation for acquiring knowledge and some teachers might have struggled for reading. Teachers have different types of teaching experience in their teacher careers. If the teachers observe the class each other they can drop different types of feedback and comment for improvement.

In the above assertion, the teacher can perceive varied natural experiences irrespective of their learning condition. In the observation of class to each other, ideas might be shared for the validation of knowledge. By exchanging ideas and views the teacher can empower himself to motivate learners with improved learning outcomes. In social cognitive theory, the teacher can succeed in their teaching with the modeling of others what they do. The school needs to manage time and effort to promote peer observation. Another participant PT3 said,

The teacher could have different potentiality and tactics for teaching content. Some teachers may know about digital technology. They can deliver the instruction in very effective ways by making modules. In observing the class, they can share methods and techniques for inculcating advanced knowledge and skills. The students also can interact with each other by using technology. In my opinion, peer observation is the best method of advancing instructional pedagogy.

Concerning to above, observing class and mentorship enhances the socialization and interaction for upgrading teaching strategies. Since the teachers have varieties of skill and knowledge for different discipline. The interdisciplinary mentorship can enrich the potentiality in respective manner with the sharing of experience. Campus need to create intra and inter faculty mentorship program by providing resource and facility.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration

Encourage interdisciplinary collaboration by organizing events or initiatives that bring faculty from different disciplines together to share ideas and perspectives.

In this context participant PT1 said,

The campus where I engage has multiple faculties with education management and humanities. The teacher who teaches is not meeting with pedagogical discourse. The interdisciplinary faculties share their views and ideas in teaching with different perspectives. In education faculty, more preference is given and in other faculties, content is focused on teaching. Education with fruitful content can be delivered based on child psychology through the mutual collaboration of interdisciplinary faculties.

Concerning to the above quotation, the interdisciplinary collaboration is very essential for sharing ideas and skills to capacitate strength of facilities. Intra and inter faculty collaboration support to interaction and mutual respect in the professional development. The mutual collaboration can create effective learning environment and raise the voice for professional tenure.

Recognition and Rewards

Recognizing faculties for their good performance in the university and rewarding faculty members for their achievements in teaching, research, and service comes under-recognition and reward. This can include awards, promotions, and other forms of acknowledgement.

In this context participant PT2 said,

I have been working for more than fifteen years in teaching the same subject in the same department. I remain in the same position as I commenced my teaching career. The university cannot announce advertisements in periodic mode for promotion. I think I might receive a resignation in the same post.

The career promotion opportunity is missing in this university. Therefore, most teachers lack motivation for university jobs and long-term engagement.

In the above assertion, the faculties need promotion after serving certain period. The regular promotion and motivation creates professional ethics in their career. The teacher actively involved in their duty if they are regularly motivated by additional benefit based on their performance. The career building opportunities are missing in the university due to the limited resources and willingness. Therefore, for achieving better learning outcomes, the universities need to offer promotional opportunity periodically and regularly.

Another participant PT3said,

The departments where I teach have more teachers as compared to others. The senior teachers are large in numbers. Until now, I have not had any opportunity to participate in research and publish articles in impactful journals. The university opens a very low number of quotas for promotion. The teacher with more experience get the opportunity and other remain not promoted in the job career.

In the above concern, the teacher working in the university is not grasping the opportunity of promotion in their job tenure. The teacher needs to be provided with professional development opportunities by allocating funds and time. By the frequent announcement of promotion advertisements with eligible criteria, the teachers are encouraged to promote their motivation and job sustainability. The universities need to make clear promotion criteria with transparency for faculty promotion that reflect a balanced assessment of teaching, research, and service contributions.

Access to Educational Technology

The provision of training for faculty with updated knowledge and resources to effectively use educational technology tools, helping them enhance the learning experience for students refers to access to educational technology.

In this context, a participant PT1said,

Delivering instruction is made easier with the use of advanced technology. Developing modules and disseminating them to students transforms teaching into effective learning for diverse learners based on their needs. In our context, the teaching and learning system falls under the traditional methods and becoming a hurdle to learning. Frankly speaking, I do not have any technical skills to engage learners in the classroom. Teaching through the lecture method is a more obstructive and teacher-centered approach. This method cannot impart skill-based advanced knowledge.

In the above narration, instruction in higher education becomes more comfortable and time-consuming with the help of technology. This type of technique makes learners engage with classroom discourse and student-centered activity. The traditional type of teaching is outdated and more teachers cannot support student learning. With the help of technology,

students themselves create a source of knowledge and disseminate it in appropriate places. So for the development of a technically competent person, the resource centers need to initiate so that they can provide technical and professional support services to university faculty, and to help them keep abreast of Instructional methods and resources, including the uses of information and Communication Technology (ICT). ICT-based technology can address the knowledge gap in the present world. After imparting education, the educator must become competent in the chosen discipline. The achieved education needs to cultivate essential knowledge and skills to run their future career. The instruction with digital pedagogy can simply be the content as per the individual interest. Therefore, the university teacher needs to compulsorily acquire digital skills for effective instruction.

Adapting to Technology

Integrating technology into teaching can enhance the learning experience, but it also requires a learning curve. Delivering instruction with digital tools and assistive devices can create a friendly platform for learners (Joshiet *al.*, 2018)^[6]. With the help of technology teacher can impart knowledge in advanced and simpler way. In this context, the participant said, Teaching through digital technology is one of the easiest and most comfortable methods for teaching. It saves time and covers more content in a short time. By this method, the student can fully engage and satisfy their activity. Most of the university teachers are far from the latest technology and updated training is lacking. In traditional teaching, the teacher needs to prepare more and more and the students are unable to engage constructively. In the above assertion, digital pedagogy is one of comfortable and result-oriented instructional techniques. In such types of teaching strategies, classroom discourse becomes fruitful and goal-oriented. The teacher's efficacy is reflected in the allotted time with optimum benefit (Bharati & Chalise *et al.*, 2017). The teacher can impart knowledge rigorously through technical support. However, the existing situation is most of the teachers are hanging with traditional teaching methods due to various reasons like time, resources and skills. As recommended by Information and Communication Policy 2073, the teacher needs adequate training in digital literacy and assistive device skills (Rana & Rana *et al.*, 2020). According to human capital theory, the investment in education needs to extend its horizon for teacher competency in instructional technology.

Networking and Collaboration

Building and maintaining professional relationships with colleagues within and outside the institution is important for collaborative research, idea exchange, and personal growth (Shah *et al.*, 2022). However, time constraints can make networking challenging. In this context participant PT2said,

I belong to the professional department and more than fifteen teachers are related to this department. The teachers never fall into discussing the teaching pedagogy and updated content but instead talks about

politics and political leader. No teacher is keeping the matter of classroom teaching in the department. Every teacher runs in his way by personal insight.

In the above concern, the teachers possess multidisciplinary knowledge and skills in the different departments. The content, pedagogy and teaching style differ as per the department. The interconnectivity among the various departments cultivates the way of exchanging ideas and knowledge discrimination in multiple prospects. So inter and intra-department discussions need to flourish for the advancement of pedagogy with a knowledge-sharing approach. Another participant PT3said, I have been teaching on the public campus since 15 years ago and we cooperate especially for pedagogy. Being the faculty of humanities, I take the idea of education for assessment purposes. The education teacher shares with us the idea about test construction and scoring. Sometimes I participate in the seminar organized by the faculty of education regarding test construction and scoring. In the above concern, the faculties are developing professionalism by sharing ideas within and outside the department. The faculties of education also initiate to organize professional development activities for the teachers. The teachers are grasping the opportunity to strengthen professional efficiency through their efforts. In such a manner, the colleges need to organize seminars and workshops in every changed context to capacitate the teacher. The entire faculty can accumulate to carry out the collaborative research.

7. Conclusion

The study intended to explore professional development policy and planning for faculties' development in higher education from the insight and perspective of teachers. From the literature, the horizon of higher education undergoing profound transformation and faculties of campuses need to raise the opportunity by addressing a variety of challenges. The dynamic interplay of shifting pedagogical paradigms, technological innovation, diverse student population and changing expectations necessitates a commitment to ongoing professional development. From the literature, it is clear that the traditional role of the teacher is transformed into a facilitator and guides and guides students towards critical thinking, problem solving and adaptability. The participant in this study urged that the faculties in higher education need to embark on a journey of self-improvement and innovation to acknowledge the challenges. Creating collaborative learning communities, training, seminars, workshops and online resources provides avenues for professional development. Moreover, fostering a culture of open dialogue, feedback exchange, and interdisciplinary collaboration can enable teachers to collectively navigate the complexities of their profession. The study's findings can affect higher education institutes' strive to create holistic and enriching learning experiences with the integral effort of teachers. By confronting the professional challenges, the policy maker in higher education can reproduce lifelong learning opportunities for learners and faculties can not only excel in their careers but also contribute significantly to the transformation of education

itself. The dedication to professional development is not just a response to challenges but also a commitment to nurturing the potential of every student and shaping the future of education.

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